

A STUDY ON THE VISCOSITY OF DECORTICATED TAMARIND SEED POWDER (TAMARINDUS INDICA, L.)

By D. B. DAS AND K. K. BASAK

Compared with other starches it has a higher initial viscosity and the rate of fall of viscosity on boiling is less. An explanation has been suggested for the change of viscosity of T. S. P. on boiling and it has been shown that the process is not exactly reversible. The lowering of the viscosity with increase in temperature has been discussed and an equation has been suggested for the relationship between viscosity and temperature. An equation has been suggested to represent the relationship between the viscosity of T. S. P. paste and its concentration. The effect of pH on the viscosity of T. S. P. has been studied and it has been shown that the T.S.P. should be gelatinised in presence of $M/1000$ sodium carbonate solution when the decrease of the viscosity of T. S. P. on boiling is almost completely arrested. A study on the effect of salt on viscosity shows that copper sulphate and zinc chloride should not be used with the T. S. P. size, but calcium chloride may be added. A probable explanation is given why the viscosity method may be accepted as a means of evaluating a starch for sizing. T. S. P. has been recommended to replace starch for jute warp sizing because of its cheapness and absence of food value.

High viscosity is a special physical property of high polymers. Another characteristic feature of the high polymeric substances is their ability to produce films of considerable tensile strength. It is likely that for a particular type of polymer, the higher its molecular weight, the stronger its film becomes, *i. e.* higher the viscosity, the greater is the strength of the film.

The best starches for sizing are those which can produce the strongest films on the warp yarns and it appears therefore that the valuation of a particular starch for sizing may be ascertained by measuring its viscosity. The viscosity method has therefore become of importance in assessing the quality of a starch and this method has been in use over a considerable period (Ermen, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1907, 26, 501; MacNider, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1917, 9, 597; Smith, *Text. Manuf.*, 1921, 47, 212). This method has also been adopted for the valuation of glue by Adhesive Research Committee (1st Report, 1922, p. 75, H. M. Stationery Office).

During the war years when the problem of supplies of starch for sizing became acute, tamarind seed powder was used largely in mills, especially in the Jute Industry and is being now used in continually increasing quantities. Some of the jute mills use other starches such as sago, maize, etc., of widely varying composition in the size mixture.

The purpose of the present work is mainly to investigate the physical properties of tamarind seed powder with special reference to viscosity and to ascertain if it can replace the other more conventional type of starches used in industry which are comparatively costly and difficult to obtain. Attempts have also been made in this paper to interpret the results in terms of molecular structure.

In the preparation of the size various substances are added for different purposes e. g. zinc chloride, copper sulphate, etc. are used as antisectics; sodium carbonate, caustic soda, borax, etc. for gelatinisation of starch, and so on. The present paper also deals with the effect of these reagents on the viscosity of tamarind seed powder.

The effects of the temperature, the time of boiling and the concentration of tamarind seed powder on the viscosity have also been studied and reported on.

EXPERIMENTAL

Partly decorticated tamarind seed powder was sieved through a 32 mesh sieve, the same sample being used throughout the whole investigation. It had an ash content of 2.55%. The sample was pale brown in colour, indicating the presence of a small amount of testa. The sago and maize had ash contents of 0.35% and 0.13% respectively.

Preparation of the Pastes—Preliminary investigations have shown that the viscosity of tamarind seed powder, like that of other starches, is dependent on the time of boiling of the paste. The paste was prepared by boiling a known quantity of the conditioned raw material with water or salt solution, as the case may be, for exactly 20 minutes, cooled, made to volume, strained through fine muslin and then used for the viscosity determinations. This concentration of the paste on dry weight was determined from its pre-determined moisture content. The paste was prepared in a glass beaker using a glass stirrer.

Viscometer and the Measurement of the Viscosity.—A British Standard Ostwald type viscometer (No. 2; Pamp. No. 188, 1929; British Standard Institution) was used in the usual way with the common precautions necessary for obtaining accurate values. For simplicity tamarind seed powder is referred to throughout this paper as T.S.P. and relative viscosity as 'viscosity'.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Boiling.—Viscosity of a starch paste usually falls with the time of boiling. As this property is of importance in evaluating the quality of a starch, the effect of boiling T. S. P. and different starches on the viscosity at 35° was studied. In these experiments attempts were made to choose the concentrations of the pastes in such a way that their initial viscosities were very near to one another. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Time of boiling.	Relative viscosity		
	T. S. P. (0.5%)	Sago (1.0%)	Maize (1.5%)
10 mins.	4.7	5.2	4.9
20	5.0	4.0	4.6
30	4.3	3.3	4.5
60	3.8	2.9	4.0
180	2.9	2.9	2.7
300	2.5	2.5	2.4

It can be seen therefore that the T.S.P. has the highest initial viscosity and the effect of boiling on the viscosity of T.S.P. is the minimum. Again, in the case of T.S.P. there is an initial rise of viscosity to a maximum, followed by the usual fall. It is of course obvious that in all starch pastes this initial rise to a maximum due to the gelatinisation of the starch granules must take place, but usually the highest viscosity passes before any measurements are made.

A good deal of confusion has arisen in the past to attempt to explain changes of properties of solution by boiling until Wehr (*Kolloid Z.*, 1939, **88**, 185, 290) made a complete treatment of the subject. It is generally accepted that boiling causes the hydrolytic destruction of the chemical linkages in the originally existing starch paste. Tamarind seed powder consists of chains linked by gluco-galacto-xylan bonds (Savur and Sreenivasan, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, **172**, 501). On boiling it is probable that these bonds are hydrolysed, thereby causing the reduction of their molecular dimensions, and hence the viscosity.

Effect of Temperature.—As the temperature has a pronounced effect on the viscosity of a starch, the take-up of the size by the yarn depends greatly on the temperature of the size. Viscosity is relatively low at high temperatures and generally increases rapidly with decreasing temperature which results in a thicker paste. At a low temperature therefore the starch will set quickly on the yarn, give an uneven coating and dust off very rapidly. A comprehensive study of the effect of temperature on the viscosity of the 0.5% T.S.P. was therefore carried out. The results are shown in Table II and illustrated by Fig. 1.

TABLE II

Temp. of the size.	Relative viscosity of T. S. P.	
	Direct.	Reverse.
25°	6.8	6.4
35°	5.0	4.7
45°	3.8	3.6
60°	2.6	2.5
70°	2.1	2.0
75°	1.9	

The viscosity of tamarind seed powder also therefore increases rapidly with the decrease of temperature. Further, this change in the case of T.S.P. is not exactly reversible. This behaviour therefore cannot be explained only by the change of the molecular structure with the change of temperature. Hence the decrease in viscosity of T. S. P. at a higher temperature is partly due to the hydrolysis of the gluco-galacto-xylan bonds of T. S. P. molecules, and mainly due to their coiling at an elevated temperature.

Attempts were made to find a relationship between the viscosity of the T.S.P. and the temperature. Shinoda and Inagaki (*Cellulose Ind., Tokyo, 1936, 12, 221*) have found a temperature effect in the cellulose acetate in various solvents which could be expressed by a relationship of the type,

$$\eta_r = Ae^{-B/t}$$

where A and B are constants, and t is the temperature. This has been verified by other workers in the case of nitrocellulose in acetone.

Linear relationship between logarithm of the viscosity and the reciprocal of the temperature has been confirmed experimentally for many liquids. After a careful study of the above results, it is found from Fig. 1 that the temperature effect on the viscosity of the T. S. P. in water may approximately be represented by

$$\eta_r^{40^\circ} = e^{100/t}$$

FIG. 1

Effect of Concentration.—Viscosity of a starch paste increases with an increase of concentration. At higher concentrations this is greater than concentration increase. In the presence of 0.02% Na_2CO_3 solution the increase of viscosity of T. S. P. at 35° with concentration is much more rapid than that in water, as shown in Table III, illustrated by Fig. 2.

TABLE III

Conc. of T. S. P. (g./100 c. c., dry wt.)	Relative viscosity		$10 \times \log_{10}$ Relative viscosity.	
	Water.	Na_2CO_3 .	Water.	Na_2CO_3 .
0.1	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.6
0.1	1.8	2.1	2.9	3.2
0.3	2.8	3.0	4.4	4.7
0.4	3.7	4.2	5.6	6.2
0.6	6.9	8.7	8.4	9.4
0.8	13.1	16.6	11.2	12.2
1.0	17.0	29.4	12.5	14.7
1.5	--	111.6	--	20.5

Various equations have been proposed to correlate the viscosity of polymers with concentration. Arrhenius (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1887, 1, 285) suggested the following equation,

$$\log \eta_r = K. c.$$

Later on others (Bradlee and Booyes, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 79, 31, 43; Fikentscher, *Cellulose Chem.*, 1932, 13, 58; Papkow, *Kunststoffe*, 1935, 25, 253) also suggested similar equations. Several equations relating to the specific viscosity with concentration and intrinsic viscosity with concentration have also been proposed.

FIG. 2

Attempts were made to find a relation between the viscosity and the concentration of the T. S. powder. Various equations were tested and it is found that in dilute solution (up to the concentration of 0.8%) Arrhenius equation holds good (Fig. 2). Above this concentration, however, the $\log \eta_r$ increases less rapidly with concentration increase. In dilute solution therefore the relationship between the viscosity of T. S. P. with water and concentration may be represented by

$$\log_{10} \eta_r = 1.4c.$$

Effect of pH.—Keeping the conditions of preparation of the starch paste and its concentration the same, it is obvious that the viscosity of tamarind seed powder will vary from pH to pH . Starches gelatinise generally in alkaline solution, and so it is anticipated that their viscosity will increase as the pH increases. On the other hand, alkalis cause degradation of starch and therefore it is to be expected that the viscosity of tamarind seed powder will reach a maximum and then decrease as the pH increases.

The effect of pH on the viscosity of 0.5% tamarind seed powder at 35° was therefore studied using citric acid-phosphate buffer, the results being shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

pH	...	4	6	7	8	9.2*
Rel. viscosity	...	4.8	5.0	5.5	5.4	5.2

* Unbuffered caustic soda solution.

If the data be plotted graphically it can be seen that the viscosity reaches a maximum at about pH 7 and falls steeply on the acidic side and slowly on the alkaline side. The nature of the curve indicates that the maximum value probably lies in slightly alkaline solution.

It is well known that the viscosity of a polymer depends on the solvent.** If the solvent is such that the attraction between the solvent and solute molecules is very great in comparison with the attraction between the solvent—solvent and the solute—solute molecules, the polymer molecules attain a more extended configuration, and hence an increase of viscosity with increase of pH , until neutral, may be explained as due to the uncoiling of the molecules at a higher pH . At a still higher pH , however, T. S. P. molecules suffer the breaking of gluco-galacto-xylan linkages to shorter chains, and hence the lowering of viscosity.

Control of the pH is of relatively minor importance for warp sizing, the whole character of the operation being determined by the higher initial viscosity and smaller change of viscosity with time. T. S. P. is therefore most suitable in dilute alkaline solution.

Effect of Alkalis.—As the above experiment shows that the viscosity increases in dilute alkaline solution, the effect of the concentration of the sodium carbonate, caustic soda and borax solutions on viscosity was studied to find the concentration of alkali required to give the maximum viscosity. The results are tabulated in Table V.

*Here the term solvent means everything comprising the solution except the polymer.

TABLE V

Conc. of alkali.	Relative viscosity of T. S. P. in		
	Caustic soda.	Sodium carbonate.	Borax.
M/10	4.0	--	--
M/25	4.9	--	--
M/50	5.3	--	--
M/100	5.5	--	7.1
M/150	--	--	7.3
M/200	5.8	5.7	7.7
M/300	5.8	--	--
M/400	5.9	--	6.9
M/500	--	--	--
M/800	--	--	6.8
M/1000	6.3	6.4	7.2

T. S. P. for warp sizing should therefore be prepared in a very slightly alkaline solution when the maximum viscosity will be obtained. This is also supported by the fact that the rate of fall of viscosity at 35° on boiling is almost arrested in M/1000 sodium carbonate (Table VI), the pH of the paste being only 7-7.5. Even if the paste is kept 18 hours at room temperature, the viscosity drops to only 4.3 in comparison with that in water to 2.8. Strong alkaline solutions, however, cause degradation of T. S. P. and lowering of viscosity and should therefore be avoided.

TABLE VI

Time of boiling.	Relative viscosity of T. S. P. in	
	Water.	M/1000 Na ₂ CO ₃ .
10 mins.	4.7	3.7
20	5.0	6.1
30	4.3	6.3
60	3.8	6.4
180	2.8	5.9
300	2.5	5.7

Effect of Salts.—The addition of moderate quantities of soluble salts to a starch paste diminishes the viscosity (Richardson and Waite, *J. Text. Inst.*, 1933, 24, 383) in a manner similar to that which has been observed for sols and gum arabic (Taft and Malm, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 874), for soluble starch (de Jong, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1924, 43, 189) or agar (Kruyt and de Jong, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 100, 250). The fall of viscosity has been ascribed either to a diminution of hydration of the colloid brought about by the electrolyte, or to a diminution of its electrokinetic potential relative to water. As some of the salts, noted below, are used in jute sizing for different purposes, their effect on the viscosity of 0.5% T. S. P. at 35° has been studied and noted in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Salt.	Conc. of the salts.	Relative viscosity.
Nil	...	5.7 Δ
Zinc chloride	M/50	4.5
Calcium chloride	M/50	5.9
Copper sulphate	M/250	2.3

The addition of copper sulphate therefore causes considerable lowering of viscosity, whereas the addition of CaCl_2 causes an increase in viscosity. Hence, if a high viscosity is aimed at, T.S.P. paste should be made up with very small amount of alkali and without the addition of copper sulphate or zinc chloride. Calcium chloride may, however, be added.

The authors record their indebtedness to the Chief Chemist, Mr. J. F. Wareham for his kind interest throughout the whole investigation and Messrs. Jardine Henderson, Ltd., for their permission to publish the paper.

GROUP LABORATORY,
 MESSRS. JARDINE HENDERSON, LTD.,
 BARANAGORE JUTE FACTORY, CO. LTD.,
 CALCUTTA-35.

Received December 10, 1949.